

TalX Workshop 3: Adaptation Evidence for Well-Adapting Places

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Introduction

A changing climate poses a wide range of impacts and risks for the UK and Ireland. To prepare for these climatic impacts, dynamic and sustainable adaptation action is needed across all sectors and tiers of society. This needs to be underpinned by an increase in the ability of organisations and communities to deliver adaptation actions in different places across Britain and Ireland.

As part of the EPA-funded Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TaIX) project, a Capability and Maturity Model (CMM) is being created for the five jurisdictions (Republic of Ireland, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales and England) that will enable and support the development and acceleration of place-based adaptation actions. This model will provide a framework that supports a combination of top-down and bottom-up adaptation measures, acting as a roadmap enabling progression on the journey towards a well-adapted place. The CMM will help those delivering place-based adaptation to address the internal barriers that they have control over by enhancing their adaptive capacity, through the development and acceleration of a range of key capabilities.

To develop the CMM a series of online co-creation workshops are being held, inviting experienced adaptation practitioners and policymakers from across the 5 jurisdiction areas to provide their insights and experiences of 'on the ground' adaptation. The first of these workshops (practitioner perspectives on well-adapting places) was held on March 29th and 30th practitioners from across the jurisdictions identified priority capability themes for inclusion in the CMM in order to enable places to become well-adapted. The priority themes included:

- Leadership and Ownership (**Leadership**)
- Research, Knowledge and Expertise (**Evidence**)
- Collaboration, cross-sectoral networks and Partnerships (**Partnerships**)
- Community Education, Engagement, Involvement and Empowerment (**Community**)
- Sustained and Secure Funding and Resource (**Resource**)

Figure 1: Themes in the Workshop Series with the theme of this workshop (Evidence) report outlined in red

These themes will form the basis of workshops (Figure 1) where they have been, and will continue to be, explored in detail. It is through the exploration of these key capabilities alongside adaptation practitioners that we will draw out the necessary detail to co-create the CMM, providing a framework to increase adaptive capacity and enable successful adaptation.

Workshop 3 - Evidence

The third TalX workshop was based on the capability theme of evidence and aimed to establish the key evidence qualities needed for good adaptation and the actions and activities necessary to develop the evidence base and support good decision-making in relation to adaptation. The workshop was targeted at experienced climate adaptation practitioners including those who both use and develop the evidence base to provide a range of perspectives from across the 5 jurisdiction areas (Appendix 1).

Evidence in the context of the workshop was defined as:

- Research, Knowledge and Expertise
- Support understanding, decision making and/or actions
- Relevant, usable, legitimate and credible including indigenous/community/lived experience
- Fitting to the audience and outcomes

In addition, the workshop participants were asked to consider the relevance of Evidence in the context of:

- Just Climate Adaptation
- Transboundary issues of place-based adaptation
- Mainstreaming
- Monitoring & Evaluation

The purpose of this workshop was to draw out the nuances of building the evidence base and supporting decision making in policy & action at different stages of adaptation to enable the co-development of the CMM.

Workshop Structure

To support workshop activities and prior to the workshop, a [pre-recorded video](#) was circulated to all participants providing an overview of the TalX project. The workshop was delivered online over one morning and included a series of introductory presentations and two work sessions (WS).

Introductory Presentations:

The presentations provided case studies on the use of evidence in climate adaptation and the challenges that occur, setting the scene for the subsequent work sessions and the discussions on evidence.

The first presentation, by Prof. Sarah Lindley (University Manchester), was on the role of socio-economic data in place-based adaptation using evidence from the Climate Just project. The Climate Just resources (www.climatejust.org.uk) were developed from a decade-long programme of research involving multiple non-academic partners. This presentation explored experiences from difference user groups showing how the resources have helped to bring positive impacts for adaptation action.

What does all of the evidence for an area suggest might be a priority for action?

Figure 2: Example from the Climate Just mapping of present day neighbourhood flood combining social and environmental data

The second case study was from Dr. James Fitton (MaREI) and included the use of different types of climate evidence at various scales to support decision-makers and practitioners develop appropriate adaptation measures, with specific examples from Ireland and Scotland including <https://climateireland.ie>; [CARO WIRE App - CARO \(Figure 3\)](#); and [Dynamic Coast](#). He emphasised the importance of research being linked to practical outcomes and being usable by the people on the ground, both in terms of the collection of further data and also the language around, and usability of, the data already collected.

CARO WIRE App

- WIRE - Weather Impacts Register for Local Authorities
 - Developed by Atlantic Seaboard North CARO
 - Inform climate risk and vulnerability assessments
 - identify areas of increasing risk and support an evidence-based approach to climate adaptation planning by local authorities
 - support the development of a Risk & Vulnerability Toolkit

TIME TO ADAPT

Figure 3: Example from the Climate Just mapping for neighbourhood flood vulnerability for the present day combining social and environmental data.

We then moved on to the Interactive part of the workshop using MIRO board (Figure 4) to allow people to contribute during the sessions supplemented by discussion. The first session was a thought shower exercise where all participants shared their thoughts on the same board before the participants were split up into breakout rooms for ease of discussion and sharing of case studies/examples.

Figure 4: Overview of the entire MIRO process (left) and zoom in on discussion in plenary as part of WS1 (right)

Work Session 1: Tales of evidence being used successfully (or not!) for better adapting places

WS1 explored what makes good evidence through the sharing of case studies of what has worked (and what hasn't) in using evidence for place-based adaptation. This consisted of a mind-map exercise in Miro, followed by discussing different examples and noting these case studies on the Miro Board in breakout groups. Participants explored how these case studies relate to evidence and have the power to be indicative of what works and what doesn't, which is equally important (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Examples of Stories from the Break out rooms for Task 2

Work Session 2: Exploring how and when evidence is relevant on the journey towards a well adapting place

WS2 involved 2 tasks, encouraging participants to think about what actions and resources they have used to develop evidence for place based adaptation, and then exploring how this changes over time in relation both to the evidence base needed and relevance to decision making. Both tasks were

carried out using exercises in Miroboard, including mind-map and maturity mapping exercises, and following this, discussions in breakout groups (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Work Session 2 tasks examples of the breakout sessions exploring the actions and resources needed for place-based adaptation and how evidence needs change over time.

Results

The presentations on Evidence helped provide deeper context on the definition of evidence for place based adaptation. Socioeconomic data that are collected for other reasons (for example census data), are vital for understanding why certain people and communities are more vulnerable to the impacts of Climate Change than others and should be used alongside the environmental data. There will always be limitations and multiple perspectives on the use of social data, but a wider range of data brings increased innovation and the opportunity for more partnerships in relation to decision making, especially at the local level. It helps coordinate responses across a range of issues and the addition of social disadvantage data strengthens climate risk assessments.

Figure 7: Diagram from Dr. Fitton's Presentation explaining the links between climatic evidence and socioeconomic processes in relation to risk

The second presentation by Dr. Fitton, provided a range of real world examples for producing and translating the evidence so that it is appropriate for practical applications. Evidence for place-based adaptation needs to be relevant and available at local scales in decision making, whilst also nested within a national approach where possible. Data should be accessible to users both in terms of access, understandability (user friendly language) and the level of detail necessary for the decision-making process.

The work sessions were coordinated via Miro, where the outputs of the working sessions are stored. They are available at: [TalX Workshop September 02nd](#), [Online Whiteboard for Visual Collaboration](#) (miro.com) and are included in the Appendices at the end of this report. The insights and outputs for each of these work sessions are summarised below:

Work Session 1: Tales of evidence being used successfully (or not!) for better adapting places (Appendices 3 &4) highlighted what evidence was considered necessary for good place based climate adaptation. The participants provided many examples of evidence relevant for decision making which can be broken down into the following broad themes:

- Risk/Vulnerability Mapping
- “Modern” Data collection & Historic Records
- Community Involvement
- Holistic evidence (combinations)
- Quality/availability Issues & Presentation of Evidence
- Oral Evidence & Local Narratives
- Action, Monitoring & Evaluation
- Sustainability of Adaptation (Carbon impacts and need to avoid maladaptation)

Some of the specific points raised were in relation to the continuity of data collection so it is comparable over time, integrating local data and stories and exploring how these fit into risk and vulnerability assessments, and communicating the need for action. Some of the challenges involve ensuring the right language is used for the audience, as technical terms can get confusing. Also, there is a need for insiders within sectors to translate and share evidence, especially when seeking consensus on action.

The biggest drivers both for evidence collection and action are “Adaptation Windows” which include legislative changes; funding opportunities; extreme weather events, major shifts in policy, and shifts in land ownership. There is also a need to think beyond the usual suspects. For data this could include the use of industry collected data, historic datasets (from shipping records to cathedrals), local business records of impacts, and oral histories, to understand local impacts of climatic events. It was also acknowledged that it can be difficult to move from short term crisis response to consideration of the needs for long-term system-based progress – especially as political and funding cycles are generally in the short to medium term.

Work Session 2: Exploring how and when evidence is relevant on the journey towards a well adapting place (**Task 1**) explored the actions and resources relevant for developing the evidence base. The key themes covering the types of actions and resources needed include:

- Collaboration
- National & International Policy as drivers/ownership
- Oral Evidence/local narratives
- Risk/impact assessments, and Modern/Historic Records
- Behavioral change/Holistic Adaptation/Learning
- Communication
- Quality/Type of Evidence

The freely available national data sets such as those from the Met Office (currently UKCP18 projections) and the independent UK Climate Change Risk Assessment are very useful for presenting

data in one place and are trusted, but stakeholders need support in understanding what they mean and how they are applicable to their local area.

Examples of collecting ground-truthed local data include the Weather Impacts Register (WIRE App) which was piloted with a number of local authorities in ROI in 2020 and allows local staff to collect local data in a standardised way. There is also a need for a variety of skills including the ability to use behavioural science to encourage change; the ability to translate research into language that the relevant stakeholders can not only understand but also use to support decision making, and toolkits to overlay important information for local people on top of mapping so that adaptation is considered in relation to the place as they understand it.

Networks of sensors allow comparable data and consistent monitoring. For example 50 new ground water stations were installed across Northern Ireland last year. Remote sensing, satellite data and drones can provide more environmental data to feed into baseline surveys, while more social data can be collected through surveys, existing social and economic datasets (such as the census) and story mapping.

The **second task** was maturity mapping to explore what evidence is needed in relation to developing the evidence baseline and also supporting decision making. For this session we asked participants to consider what was needed to start the journey in place-based adaptation and then to think about what would be needed to maintain a well adapting place. We have split the responses into 3 levels in Appendix 6. However, when exploring the answers, we have summarised them into three high level sections with some overlap visible between sections in the figures below for developing the evidence base (figure 8) and supporting decision making (figure 9):

Figure 8: High level capacity maturity stages for capacities relevant for developing the evidence base in relation to the beginning of the journey to place based adaptation; on the journey and for a well adapting place

Figure 9: High level capacity maturity stages for capacities relevant for evidence base in relation to decision making at the beginning of the journey to place based adaptation; on the journey and for a well adapting place

Stages of maturity in relation to evidence for climate adaptation have been split into 3 different levels which are described below:

Level 1 – Know what you and your partners know and start to identify what you don’t know

Know what evidence is available already and what is accessible relatively easily. This could include nationally available datasets, research produced through local industry, government, and/or research institutions and also local stories/examples and local/regional archive data. Understand permissions for its use, how often it is collected, the resolution and the quality of the evidence. Ensure that a range of evidence is sourced including environmental, social and economic data, but don’t collect data for the sake of it, try to ensure it is relevant to the scope defined by the partnership developed vision for a well adapting place. Good evidence for communicating climate change impacts comes in a variety of forms including historical image databases, building weather records, census data, public surveys,

tree rings as well as forecasting, models, satellite imagery and mapping. Map out which partners can both provide, understand and could develop new data sources. It is vital to map out the gaps in evidence and expertise and to fill these gaps as these are the first known unknowns.

In the first stage of the journey, it is the perfect time for quick wins, both communicating what is being done well to share with others (i.e. developing user friendly case studies) and also taking advantage of any “adaptation windows”. These are potential external catalysts which may include a change in legislation – leading to time bound action which must be completed legally and therefore a shift in prioritisation of which evidence to collect. Other examples might include an extreme weather event such as flooding, which triggers reactive funding for action and research to reduce future impacts, changes in land ownership which may alter the accessibility of land and/or potentially its function, something which could be highly relevant when considering microclimates and potential adaptation actions such as shoreline management, habitat restoration and floodplain zoning.

Map out stakeholders who might have more evidence which could be relevant and how they will understand and use that evidence. Ensure that a communication plan is developed by any partners so when they are talking about the evidence they understand each other and the evidence, and feel confident making or supporting decisions for future adaptation action. There is a need from the beginning to build trust between partners and stakeholders within the scope of the place in order for them to be transparent with data they have available and honest about levels of understanding in order to successfully build capacity.

Level 2 – Starting to fill the gaps, make decisions and build the evidence base

Once the initial ground work has been completed in the starting phase, it is time to start doing. There is a need for the different organisations within the place to start taking responsibility for both risks and actions and start setting SMART targets to fill the gaps in the evidence, based on the priorities needed for further decision making. It is vital that any partnership works together to build the evidence base and seeks to prioritise where funding is needed in areas of highest known risk, while also building the evidence base to fill unknown risk gaps. In order to do this it is important to carry out risk and vulnerability assessments, taking into account people, assets and nature, and building business cases in order to take the most appropriate action. There needs to be a shift towards more proactive evidence gathering (rather than just reactive) and setting up the long-term monitoring and evaluation to understand and track changes, using adaptation indicators if actions are reducing climate risk to a place. Adaptation indicators are complicated, as it is the absence of damage and loss that is being measured, however, these indicators are continually under development, so horizon scanning to keep updated on best practice from elsewhere and sharing local best practice is vital to keep building a better and more relevant evidence base. Developing cross-sectoral guidance will support the sharing of knowledge and policy development and help decision-making become more consistent. Workshops can be used both to gather and share the latest evidence with stakeholders in the most suitable format, as well as getting live feedback to ensure any communication strategy for sharing evidence is working, and if not, how it needs to change.

Level 3 – There is always more to learn and we can always get better in a well adapting place

In a well adapting place the vision of reducing impacts from climate risk would be achieved. There would be good working relationships between the partners who would be sharing evidence transparently and in easily understandable formats. Long term funding and expertise would be in place to ensure that monitoring and evaluation was happening at the right spatial and temporal frequencies so that shifts in indicators would be spotted early and there would be plans in place to take the relevant action. When extreme events happen then there would be scenarios, forecasting and storylines predicting the likely impacts so the relevant teams will be ready to play their roles to limit loss and damage. There would be regular checks to ensure the appropriate evidence is being collected at the right time and place and ensuring all data collected is fed live (after proofing) into an easily accessible shared database which can quickly produce dashboards, maps, checklists and other communication tools suitable for the intended audiences. Models will continue to be ground-truthed and honed by real time data collection across scales, from satellite data to mobile apps in which the public can report problems or possible solutions into early warning apps. Big data projects continue to hone the models for forecasting and also help evidence be integrated into complex systems and mainstreamed into cross-sectoral decision-making (from marine protected area management to housing developments, infrastructure and business policy). The public are generally happy as evidence is reducing the impact of climate risks on their lives, evidence that is relevant to their area has been shared and they have had the opportunity to contribute to the data base and be directly involved in the process. They would also be able to access risk profiles relevant to them to help with their personal decision making from buying a house, cycling to the shops or planning an outdoor event.

At this stage of adaptation there should be an overarching vision that is always in sight in order to drive transformational change that extends beyond typical geographical boundaries. By integrating adaptation evidence into all aspects of governance and place-based decision-making, climate risks and impacts will be minimised.

Conclusions and Next Steps

The workshop helped draw out insights and information on evidence for adaptation planning and actions from the experiences of the participants across the five jurisdictions of Britain and Ireland. This helped identify the challenges of building and maintaining an evidence base that is relevant for decision making for places beginning adaptation initiatives right through to those at more advanced stages of adaptation, particularly with regards to understanding what you need to know and how to build the evidence base.

The workshop highlighted that good adaptation evidence is varied in type, and a range is needed in order to ensure that the vulnerable are not left behind. Data collected includes social, environmental, biological, and economic sources and everything from peer reviewed scientific papers, national databases and models to local stories which provide relevance, colour, and higher resolution for local impacts and decision making. It was acknowledged that it is difficult to get funding and resources in place for long term evidence gathering and quite often this funding is reactive to extreme events and shifts in policy. However, participants still accepted that strategies are needed to fund long-term collaborative cross-sector evidence gathering.

The need for Evidence to be translated beyond numbers on a page into a language that the people understand was emphasized, and the use of infographics, visuals and stories, to put evidence and scenarios into perspective was encouraged in order for evidence to be used effectively in decision-making.

Overall, this workshop stressed the need for an effective framework for practical application in the UK and Ireland in order to support adaptation development. We will use the qualities and actions identified by the participants experience and expertise alongside our ongoing literature review on adaptation capabilities (including evidence) as a basis to create a draft Capability Maturity Model (CMM).

The TalX team would like to thank all the attendees and especially the speakers, for their active participation and willingness to share their insights and experience in order to promote and enable climate adaptation actions across the five jurisdictions.

Appendix 1: Participant list for the workshop

Workshop 3- Evidence		
Participant	Country - Organisation	Country
Eugene Farrell	NUI Galway	Ireland
James Fitton	Climate Ireland/ University College Cork	Ireland
Sarah Lindley	Manchester University	England
Robyn Pender	Historic England	England
Andrew Thomas	Aberdeen University	Scotland
Anat Prag	SNIFFER	Scotland
Liam Scott	Mayo County Council	Ireland
Amy Bell	Climate NI	Northern Ireland
David Mellett	Mayo County Council	Ireland
John Early	DAERA Climate Unit	Northern Ireland
Hannah Fluck	Historic England	England
Thomas Gardiner	NI Water	Northern Ireland
David Charles	Strathclyde University	Scotland
David Harkin	Historic Environment Scotland	Scotland
Clive Walmsley	Welsh Government	Wales
Christine Baker	Fingal County Council	Ireland
Hans Visser	Fingal County Council	Ireland
Larissa Naylor	Glasgow University	Scotland

Appendix 2: Workshop Agenda

Background

As part of the Irish EPA funded Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TalX - www.Talx.ie) project we are developing a Capability Maturity Model (CMM) to help progress climate adaptation across the UK and Ireland (taking action to prepare for and adjust to both the current effects of climate change and the predicted impacts in the future). The CMM aims to support adaptation practitioners across the UK and Ireland in advancing planning for, and implementation of, effective place-based adaptation.

Following on from the initial workshop exploring practitioner perspectives on well-adapting places, 5 are a priority for advancing effective place-based adaptation and we will be holding a series of workshops exploring these capabilities in detail.

Select Practitioners from across the UK and Ireland are invited so we hope it will be a useful learning and sharing process for all involved and will contribute towards building a stronger climate adaptation network.

This workshop will focus on evidence, knowledge and expertise and how it can help us understand the challenges and support decision making around place-based adaptation relevant plans and action.

Useful Information:

- In advance of the workshop and to make the most efficient use of time available, participants are asked to view a video presentation providing an overview of the TalX project. The video presentation has been made available [here](#)
- To support workshop activities, MIRO and Mentimeter platforms will be used. We recommend that you familiarise yourself with these tools prior to the workshop so that you can get the most out of the sessions. You can find a short introductory video on how to use Miro [here](#) and Mentimeter [here](#)

Time	Title	Topic	Presenter
10:00	Welcome, Introduction and Project Overview	Overview of the aims and agenda of the workshop	Barry O'Dwyer & Jade Berman
10:15	Keynote Speakers -	Sarah Lindley – University of Manchester – Climate Just James Fitton – University College Cork – Climate Ireland	Sarah Lindley James Fitton
10:40	Work session 1	Interactive discussion to explore the what makes good evidence, sharing of stories of what has worked (and what hasn't) in using evidence for place-based adaptation	TalX Team
11:10		Break	
11:15	Work session 2	Interactive discussions to explore how and when evidence is most relevant at different stages and how it is used on the journey towards a well adapting place.	TalX Team
12:20	Wrap Up and Close	Summary of the workshop outputs and Next Steps	TalX Team

Appendix 3: WS1-Task 1-Examples of evidence shared relevant for decision-making and/or for making progress in place based climate adaptation?

Evidence Theme	Example
Risk/Vulnerability mapping	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCC independent climate change risk assessment (CCRA) • SEPA food risk maps and Flood Hazard and Risk Information Tool • Flood maps e.g. SEPA, OPW, EA • SEPA UPSM data, BGS made ground data, OS historic maps, SEPA flood maps • There has been some useful work through the Defra Flooding Roundtable on SME vulnerability, which is often overlooked • Historic Env Sector Wales Vulnerability assessment of historic assets • NRW developed range of vulnerability assessments for marine and coastal sites/biotopes around Welsh coast • NRW - National vulnerability assessment of protected areas in Wales used to identify adaptation priority sites • CLIMATE RISK AND OPPORTUNITY ASSESSMENT FOR GLASGOW CITY REGION - https://www.crc-assessment.org.uk/ • Councils in NI using the LCLIP method in adaptation planning • Climate Ireland: Semi-Quantitative Climate Change Risk Assessment Method for the Local Authority Sector
Modern and Historic records	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atkins GIS model and report for the Glasgow Climate Neutral Innovation District • some examples emerging from Historic England work with Fjordr ltd on historic environment understanding of watercourses, local history and flood management. also exploring this in the AHRC funded CLANDAGE project led by Neil MacDonald at U of Liverpool • Impacts of severe weather - Climate NI has an Extreme Weather L=Timeline • Soil moisture and temp data • Climate projections • local archives used for understanding flood and drought risk • CCC • local community archives and local society records • Coastal mapping project using historic data and new LIDAR data • maintenance records for properties and owners

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data from cathedra quinquennial reviews (monitoring changes in rainfall patterns etc) • Historic environment information including archaeological information, landscape history and local (vernacular) heritage - local historic environment records, landscape characterizations are examples • microclimate sensor networks • Historical rainfall data • Lidar Data • Dynamic Coast data • salt water intrusion data and contaminated land data are needed to support land-based adaptation • DFI Rivers Agency flood web mapping system • LIDAR DATA
Community involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence? What are the enablers and barriers on coastal communities to adapt? these go from: mobilization; information; networking; funding; evidence of "how do they know they are adapting"? • Community engagement to think about what futures they would like • garden diaries/logs for large managed diaries and landscapes for monitoring local changes • At what stage are communities co-creating? the Vulnerability Indices are important but they need to subsume a community perception and experience • We used the Climate Ready Clyde risk and opportunity assessment to inform the SEA for the adaptation strategy and action plan. The risk assessment was also a high profile piece of work - many folk involved in developing - helped build community and commitment to action - the process as important as the product. • Community Research: Verifying macro climate impact data, locating additional climate hazards, and explaining who/what is vulnerable. • Providing strong recommendations for how to engage communities and key groups in climate adaptation going forwards. • Prioritizing systems to strengthen for adaptation • exploring how to increase community capacities.
Holistic evidence (combinations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International context: many donors will invest in participatory climate / vulnerability / risk / assessments with communities to inform planning. This enhances relevance and ownership of the evidence • Combining science and social evidence as a basis of convincing others (Local Authorities, National Government, Sectoral agencies)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outer Hebrides: combining scientific data, range of evidence on assets and hazards (future/past e.g Nature Scot/Dynamic Coast/Local Authority) and community perspectives on risk and vulnerability: consolidated evidence presented in the form of maps for local analysis and local ownership of decisions. Very powerful in showing Capacities at local level (from which to build upon) • We've been looking at the really massive problem of water-handling and drainage adaptation - and the critical components for solutions either fall between silos, or aren't in the room (specifically Highways England, and some of the water companies). • A behavioural science aspect is v important assess how we can encourage cultural shifts in behaviour • Indices of multiple deprivation e.g. https://www.gov.scot/collections/scottish-index-of-multiple-deprivation-2020/ • A lot of the problem has been a focus on market-led solutions - there is so much vital work that can be done if we stress things like behaviour, but that won't make anyone rich... • I've used high level evidence from national assessments to begin building the business case/ gaining support for increased action to adapt in cities, regions and localities
Quality/availability Issues and Presentation of Evidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense check: who is the object of the evidence? Scope for an us and them situation researchers and "community groups"? • Interview data from practitioners about windows of opportunity and barriers for adaptation • visualizations of coastal change to aid the public, politicians to identify different futures and social economic valuation of these. • Quality and availability of evidence/data • Business case development for senior mgt • Economic costings of severe weather
Oral Evidence/local narratives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • oral history used for understanding storm event impact • Lived experience from local residents - community mapping of impacts affecting them • traditional and local knowledge relating to land management and local biodiversity and land response to changing weather and climate • Community recollections of events etc
Action, Monitoring and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UK Water Industry Research reports specifically related to Adaption and planning • Future focused 'likelihood data' on climate hazards • there is a critical need to build into existing structures and not re-invent the wheel; in Ireland we have Education & Training Boards that are very efficient...they can engage in adaptation with communities • There is also a time-frame dimensions - somethings require thinking at different time frames, from short term crisis management to longer term consequences

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU guidelines for project managers and CRC Accelerator tool - https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/knowledge/tools/guidelines-for-project-managers • Use of UKCIP tool to use media reports of extreme weather events as evidence of need for place based adaptation with LAs • FRAW Revised national flood data for Wales that along with some social data is used to inform infrastructure priorities • CARO Weather Impacts Register (WIRE) - Mobile data collection tool for LA staff to log the impacts of weather events. MapViewer and Data Dashboard for staff to view and analyse the collected data.
Sustainability of Adaptation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need to think about carbon impacts is critical - not least, the lifespan of adaptations and therefore the long term costs. Really needed to avoid maladaptation.

Appendix 4: WS1-Task 2 – Tales of Evidence being used successfully (or not) for better adapting places

Successful	Lessons to Learn
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vulnerability indices - informs vulnerable areas - needs to be used correctly with communities • Talking with communities to enhance granular data - what does this mean at the local level, e.g. outer Hebrides pilot looking at issues around hazard, impacts and vulnerability. • Marry community and evidence together - Scotland has some good mechanisms but has a way to go • Convincing communities • Aberdeen adapts employed arts to engage the local community. Imagine the future • Evidence need to natural assets - Maharees, 9 million per year • Shoreline modelling of change - Solution orientated adaptations (Nature-based) in the Maharees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lots of evidence but no funding
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • two aspects - using evidence from others - using our own evidence. How can we capture evidence and make better decisions. Uni of Liverpool project - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • challenge of being heard by the right people

<p>using archives to influence community resilience to climate change. Also supporting contractors to feed in to decision making</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language really important - different language used across sectors - need to recognise and explain what we mean • There is also a time-frame dimension - somethings require thinking at different time frames, from short term crisis management to longer term consequences • Welsh woodland trust example - looking at how tree cover would change microclimate - really good example - where work will continue. • NI Water - use industry research. NI is unique re. topography and ground water - particularly in Belfast - considering moving back to using ground water - might be a better option for customers - using the rounded context - with changing rainfall - river water deteriorating - have to think about. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • another challenge is the complexity and need for 'systems' thinking to understand and present information • Identified language as a key challenge - the first think we had to do was clarify a focus on adaptation rather than mitigation. Working with Climate Ireland was a huge benefit - providing acc • Confusion around 'climate drivers' 'hazards' 'risks' and ' vulnerability' - these all require subtly different information and evidence but are often conflated or confused • Baseline - really important - we missed an opportunity to baseline - doing loads of great work sustainable catchment but would missed opportunity to baseline • trickier - working with NFFU wales - trying to look at resilience to CC and funding options. They have been up for funding collection of data but when you talk to the unions about changing how farming works you come up against a brick wall - v complex - any outsider coming to talk about it is very challenging • All the rivers in mid wales flood - estate agencies make no reference to flood rise - similarly on the coast - you CAN SEE THE COAST ERRODING - YET PLANNING PERMISSION STILL GRANTED. There is a lot of skepticism and a lack of awareness • Data, data and more data - creates evidence - we have to be careful about assuming about issues without having the evidence. Issue with water shortages - example of overstressing and longer term planning
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interested parties around the table • Good partners and a range of evidence • Dynamic Coast Data for coastal adaptation having all the relevant stakeholders around the table • LCLIP-local media and record weather related event using local media -to show extreme weather events now • Climate Change Risk Assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wales- (NRW) risk assessment - wasn't as useful because there was no structure and partnerships • Generic evidence isn't of any use • The council knows where their problem areas are but they need site specific information for coastal defenses • Always a risk of public perception affecting what/when data is released

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lots of evidence gathered for the CCRA. Research projects fed into the technical reports Used this to relate it to cost for local authorities Met Office Heat Packs - recently developed a pilot for Belfast. Still progressing National Flood Maps LCLIP used to help LAs in Wales understand their vulnerability across range of depts and understand extreme weather has costs so make case Climate Ready Clyde - research on heat in Glasgow At HES we used BGS and SEPA data to look at current climate risk from various nat hazards. The results of this then factored into the investment prioritization process for the properties we care for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some local councils told not to look at particular adaptation solutions because they won't be implemented (no resource)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Ed council exploring land based adapt options - interviews with cross cutting team members in councils in England too to explore awareness of adaptation Larissa's paper 'Windows of Opportunity' - windows and wagons https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/9/8/1408/htm Trusted sources often work more at local level - centralised data can be far too standardised in some circumstances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Making room for river - Dutch relocation and bridge project - about public conversations around public good - UK may not be good at that Issues around urgency and saliency Historic England - drainage issues - need data and evidence Issues around public good - e.g. flood risk infrastructure public good, domestic property not - cross over with human geography and social science and economics not just data Need to raise awareness - you don't have to be as vulnerable as you are told - e.g. builders or homeowners fearing contamination and damage - need correct information and advice - need to plan in advance City of Ed strategic plan didn't mention coastal at all despite location City of Ed project - economist costing park on coast rather than houses Inner city parts of old towns - number of examples - one of most important is working with small businesses in Hebden Bridge- finding out that businesses didn't have insurance coped better, if wrong info from insurers this detracted from preparation and recovery- small biz often find it hard to get insurance - Defra roundtable on this currently

	exploring topic. Many stakeholders not in room. Nat flood forum have problems in being open minded about what resilience can mean - rewarding people for being resilient. Don't want tick box exercise - need tangible benefits
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Appendix 5: WS2-Task 1 – What actions/resources have you used to develop the evidence base

Theme	Action/Resource
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to speak a common language - research should not be siloed - considered as part of what is important to the place - Outer Hebrides, used dynamic coasts to overlay on info on natural assets - used as part of a consultation process with people. - Powerful tool that respond to different elements of what is important. - Thinking about adaptation in the place • Note requirement for consultancy expertise for some sectors e.g. water • collaborative agreements to pull together shared resources • Decisions need to be had at community level - for local data • Working with a range of orgs. on a range of issues. – Maherees • Depts of Gov not talking to one area - one message to communities about rejuvenation whereas don't have correct CC data • Academics not valuing practice enough - CCC relies on published papers • From research perspective - knowledge exchange fellowship useful. Despite limited academic publications, did get lots of traction eg marine plan, if LN didn't have time to sit on steering committee, that wouldn't have happened, similar Edi Council - built trust, now have good relationship can challenge on their policies or proposals - because being closely involved with them - know who the right person to contact is - a lot of work that goes on that is under recognized • Climate Ready Clyde - Risk and opportunity assessment (co-developed with org).
National/ International Policy Drivers/Ownership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engineering solutions-to coastal adaptation- opw has to fund adaptation - you need them to listen to solutions other than hard/grey adaptation • European Technical Guidance

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You need the right attitude from national government - they have to be willing to use the adaption solutions the evidence recommend • cost-benefit- analysis but still need the government to listen • Government have to take ownership of difficult situations • The Adaptation Capability Framework • Evidence is slow - need academics who are willing and allowed and get credit for doing slow research - be available and connected in order to make relevant data and policy changes - need capacity to step out of academic lens to shift policy and practice eg Edinburgh exa • lack of clear national programmes for information in England is a real challenge • Ada actions influenced by private sector offering • Window opening requires a lot of time and effort and input from academics /scientists - hard graft - that needs to be better recognised (as it doesn't count as research impact despite real world impact) • Capability planning need road map not like green building raod map tough - not good not ambitious enough
<p>Oral Evidence/local narratives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speaking to the importance of local people • Lived experience is very important • Stories from folks working at our properties (Historic England) (lived experience of weather events) • Maps and post-its to capture local knowledge • CDP PhD student is developing an interactive documentary approach to gather local evidence • especially different/conflicting perspectives
<p>Risk/impact assessments, and Modern/Historic Records</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community-based impact assessments - resulting in rainwater harvesting - Talked about basic need of access to water • NI Dept of Infrastructure and DEARA looking at coastal infrastructure and nature conservation, coastal erosion mgmt - project looking at LIDAR - feeding into DFI flood mapping - info used to inform planning decisions and prioritise need for action • In the Outer Hebrides we carried out climate impact interviews with major organisations - process helped us identify how climate change is impacting their priorities, services and assets. The process of meeting with them also helped with relationship building and developing wider understanding of why climate adaptation is relevant for them • site based observation and ad hoc reporting of issues • hazard mapping • Toolkits for individual assets risk - Scotland - develops risk register for a project • remote sensing - e.g. drone survey • Need aerial photos of the past etc

- NI using info from flood mapping to plant trees in high risk catchment - woodland grants being targeted at areas of most need
- risk local decision making don't have relevant local information or influenced by local political pressures, Norfolk require relocation of communities WITHIN community as a whole - this notion that some things are restrictive that prevent progressive choices
- Climate Ireland: Semi-Quantitative Climate Change Risk Assessment Method for the Local Authority Sector. To be completed by end 2021
- historic data, eg Weather temp, rainfall
- historic mapping and archaeological landscape data
- UK CCRA data/info on key climate risks
- Challenge between data and evidence based on historic impacts versus modelling and projections
- Scharp project in Scotland - coastal erosion on cultural heritage - using local info to groundtruth higher level data <https://scapetrust.org/>
- site based monitoring e.g. of groundwater
- Use of climate projections by LAs for adaptation planning
- Soil C stock estimates
- Soil based studies to understand P decay, mining and effect on runoff, whether point load or dispersed
- using archives and diaries as past weather logs for climate modeling
- installing a network of sensors
- Veg surveys
- Field based experiments on impacts of land use and management on biodiversity and C fluxes
- NI Climate Adaptation programme - take CCC and CCRA - overheating, looked over 190 stakeholder monuments - health estates, schools, overheating an issue
- Climate change projections at the national level
- Tap into national datasets that are freely available
- Weather Impacts Register (WIRE) was piloted with a number of LAs during 2020. Preparing for implementation in all LAs in coming months. Data collection by LA staff
- Soil GHG emission estimation and how affected by land use and weather
- The National P balance study to understand the P Cycle in NI from all inputs and outputs
- Groundwater monitoring stations. c50New station in NI over the last year.
- Met Office datasets (observations and UKCP18 projections)

Behavioral change/Holistic Adaptation/Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undertaking our own assessments of climate risk • From practitioner perspective - Suffolk and Norfolk using 100 year erosion line to make decisions on planning / home / land use decisions - to ensure properties not at risk and if houses not suitable link to social housing database • Need info for adapting buildings and how to avoid maladaptation and use this to inform new builds and development - EPCs, Hist Eng act as coord • Survey on behavioural change and Perceptions of changing risk over time - bad flood event in NI 2017/18 • How impacts are measured can be challenging - things you care about most can be most difficult to measure • Some of the most satisfying work has been with social scientists - working with community members to understand what they want and need to know. Language barrier in wales • Expert teams eg customer behaviour change • recognise the best solutions • Perception that higher demand for water is linked to COVID - think also linked to weather and climate • gathering data that assesses assumptions and allows adaptive pathway thinking is so important • Behavioural science should be employed to encourage change, this is evidence, particularly for a cultural shift
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Example of presenting info differently re. P - step in the right direction • research focus has been on data - can't do in isolation - relatively few people are actually interested in the numbers • we are starting to explore story mapping • case studies to illustrate range of issues and responses and lessons learned • need to develop 'decision pathway' tools that reflect iterative approach. starting to do this in the Landscape Futures project (AHRC funded, Uni Exeter led) • and artists/ creatives to develop climate storylines - trying to make climate trends and projections info more impactful and relevant for community groups/ individuals - strike a balance between staying true to the science and also using language and impacts that resonate with people • Need to show positive vision of the future • The media has improved how they tell the story of weather events • Extreme weather timeline - climate ni - updated adhoc • language is so important but also recognition of temporal connection with places and the relationship that brings. biocultural heritage is relevant here

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historic England - evidence on vernacular architecture - need ppl to understand a lot of the vernacular architecture will cope well in high temperatures - what buildings cope less well are modern , glass buildings and new domestic properties which are less appropriate • HE Env Agency projects target end result of flooding - communities being impacted rather than where it needs to be - at catchment area work - seeing bad decision making that will cause distress as it won't solve problem - trying to get through to govt band aids won't make it better, will make it worse, need to show them horror stories if you don't get info right but also show them if you do, you get these big rewards - it's about messaging • Work with artists to visualize • Info is not just ad-hoc its focused on things that have gone wrong, rather than what has gone right - risk scaring people - need to bring together good practice
Quality/Type of Evidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of data available is an issue - difficulties in applying models locally - developed web viewer map to provide access to data. Forms the basis for community citizen science project • Evidence needs from Suffolk and Norfolk speak to businesses about impacts but don't capture data about biz day losses to inform planning decisions - right evidence about impacts is not being captures and that evidence isn't necessarily shared with the right people • Sometimes the local lived experience is exaggerated or just wrong - problem of citizen science • Credibility - you need reliable evidence • No standard models to predict future climate - need that in place • Impact on CCRA overlying on certain kind of data and reporting that may not be most robust or reliable • Datasets indicating that you may be 'safe' but given extreme events - this can be untrue and can erode trust • Need saliency and credibility and regular updates of evidence • Some people are nervous using data at site level - limitations are built in to how you can use that data • head of place Edinburgh - want to keep building for 300 - 400 years • Ad -hoc evidence base - dependent on project or building e.g. particular air flow issues, or building issues - stock take of looking at situations where there were issues

Appendix 6: WS2-Task 2 – Maturity Mapping

Level 1	Level 2 (double listed)		Level 3
Connecting Groups together - Show that all groups are in this together, e.g. show everyone that they are not on their own	Climate change impacts for my life	Integrating climate change evidence into development planning, a key capability	Cross sectoral evidence base - capturing all interactions between and sectors, areas
Understanding of not taking action - information translated into relevant/usable information	Feasibility studies - Climate risk and resilience assessment - Risks, Cost of measure and of not implementing them (Climate Ready Clyde)	Decentralisation - bring decision making to a more localised level and evidence too. Deliberate efforts to raise up groups to participate more effectively	Research funded by EU in early 90's - policy recommendations on fire risk provided to EU in mid-1990's - clearly lip service to changing anything - see this time and time again. Lip service to change - put engaging with policy
How will the place be impacted by climate change -high level	Intersections between adaptation and green spaces, mitigation etc	Considers objectives of all stakeholders - ensures that we avoid maladaptation	Commercial interest trumps all - forestry plantations
capture relevant base data, consider data frequency required and analysis techniques	Looking at Adaptation as part of wider issues (transport, mitigation)	Evidence that local groups are reflected in the process	Need to understand why evidence/ academic research is not used
high-level (summary) understanding of climate projections	Valuing social, environmental components	properly understand the challenges and be honest about unknowns	We urgently need long-term data - so pressing for funds to keep projects going would be very useful

start with history of a place - the history of people in it, and the history of its landscape and biodiversity	Knowing priorities - looking at what evidence is useful	how do you embed long term thinking in short term economy driven decisions? its a huge barrier	This story is familiar - as to why nothing happens - large amount of work happens but it's acted on
Cathedral planning commission - takes into account climate change when making decisions - are buildings able to cope with changes - use valuing systems to give structure - get people to think about climate change - think in this way of values and significance gets them to think about things in different way - links to capable	understanding the vernacular heritage - the local and traditional knowledge of the landscape, people, practices and buildings. what works well? what could work better? what is no longer done but could be re learned? not all local and traditional knowledge is currently 'living' but it doesn't mean it can't be relevant and relearned	agility and ability to respond to crisis but method to adapt to longer term considerations and not pursue short term benefit at expense of long term resilience	practical tools for gathering information and reflect upon effectiveness, being prepared to stop or change practices. recognising that there will be policy 'dead ends' that may be superseded by events - doesn't mean they were wrong at the time but not necessarily right forever
Local consultation and with policy makers (as above - building trust is vital)	infographics really important - different means of communication (throughout)	use of advanced data analytics	Outer Hebrides work as a larger group - place based groups
using the past to help contextualise change into the future - can we reasonably ask people to imagine a different future if they can't travel to a past?	be prepared for the thing that you think is most interesting or most important NOT to be the thing that the people you are trying to engage think is most important or interesting - it doesn't necessarily matter - use what the people you are trying to engage think it most interesting if it brings them in to the conversation.	the importance of integration - complex systems and we need to be integrated for these approaches	Demonstrate impacts happening elsewhere and use this to show the impacts in your own area - Do this at a national level
Look at National available data - what climate can you expect and how will it change	listening and hearing what is being said - this isn't as easy as it sounds. finding different ways to do this is complex and	Feedback and consult with communities, perhaps reassess. Engagement with policy makers	Working with partners and in-depth analysis and sharing with stakeholders how areas are managed

	requires a range of skills, some familiar, others less so		
Draw out local knowledge and lived experience	case studies of past impacts	Inventory of relevant climate hazards datasets	Need total public uproar that there's no change in policy/protection where the evidence exists
Persuading communities - show how places have adapted historically - previous impacts	case studies of adaptation projects	Data visualisation and presentation in appropriate ways - this is vita	Stocktake of info - identify gaps - Allows direction of research needs
Identify other areas also affected regionally -off the back of Fairbourne - planned to do	worth checking out the Kassandra project - we have a project looking at this BIM based decision tool at Ironbridge gorge - its and integrated decision tool for resilience - https://www.kassandraproject.org/	Creating appropriate info graphics/dashboards to inform	Prioritisation of actions / funding
Feel have to make decisions based on values - evidential and community values, need structure (STERO instructions for heritage) - informs options appraisal and gives voices to all including those often left out	identify potential 'adaptive windows' - those opportunities for decisions and to change things, are there cycles of decisions where these opportunities need to be realised? (things like new ownership, local planning cycles, farm environment plans, strategic plans, policy reviews etc) but also post crisis points often present opportunities to learn and revisit what works	Using cloud processing etc and data integration from common data environment	
Prioritise funding - putting resource where it is needed most based on data and evidence needs	Integrate different types of data	Risk & Vulnerability Assessments	
REFS policy needs can be manipulated	Decide what evidence is needed to address key questions (assuming these have been identified in first stage)	Appropriate legislation to drive change using the evidence	

Legislative landscape influences what evidence gaps can be addressed - moves from something nice to do that has to be done	Collect data at appropriate temporal and spatial scales (this is a big challenge for soils - and not always done well)	Can't build in floodplains and within 100m of an eroding shoreline - guidance for planning exists on this - policy needs to start relating to future flooding	
Building trust is a long term process - e.g. with farmers	if biocultural heritage is relevant here then a recent publication but INHERIT on this (out today - launch later today) may be of interest - lots in there about community involvement and justice	Cost analysis at a national level to face the problems - changes in legislation - can project that through time to drive change	
What do we need to safeguard now to give us options for maturity	Detailed study from every angle and provide the options that are available - transparency on what decision-making is based on	Need a blanket ban on development in at risk areas	
What land is climate resilient to build on?	Community have been made aware of the risks but still choose to build - buy - places won't do anything if there's no policy	Various levels of intervention - how it will use the evidence have	
Identify what good looks like in the longer term - e.g. 2050	Public perception of willingness for adaptation actions - survey gb - support from the public	Communication between all involved in adaptation in an area	
Sometimes research pushed as its pet projects of academics rather than what is actually needed by policy and decision makers	What support is there for the defence of private property - from a national perspective - surveys to see if the wider community would be behind this	Make sure there is studies done on it - place based	
Changes to funding models	Problem when you don't have a national plan/policy/legislation	Money is a huge driver -you need more resources available to implement solutions that evidence suggest	
	Stark differences between mainland Scotland perceptions and Island perceptions	High-level evidence is there but isn't acknowledged and respected by local community	

	Engage with the local communities when making these decisions	Dynamic coast had an external motivator (train track fell into sea) - they then looked into their own area	
	Can work with consultants and communities to identify the risks	Make sure the studies are framed within the national structure - infrastructure and tourism - form networks and demonstrate collective hazards and adaptation options	
	Workshops to get people's perceptions and ideas about the loss of their cultural heritage	Questions around place, and climate change within the census - think about the future	
	Recognise your adaptation response to the challenge	Research targeted to inform policy gaps which require additional supporting info	
	Working groups established - to prioritise options, risk owners then discuss to propose and assess delivery targets - ada plan is for 5 years - moving recently risk ratings going from research to further action needed - level of risk and timing pressures and timeframes influence funding	Assistance with non-monetary value analysis i.e. land value may be £15k per acre but land may provide social benefits in terms of access, recreation, well being etc	
	CCRA3 response to be laid in govt in Jan NI saying accept risk and prioritise options then - where there are research needs, we identify what research need	Informing - Localised targeted support schemes e.g. under EFS - special projects	
	NI relies on CCC data - independent advice on CCRA - govt departments use this advice	Planning policy / planning decisions	
	Link DM to SDGs	Evaluation to be used in different forms	

	Accessible and live data	Is there best practice that can be adapted?	
	Not enough £ to M & E - major impediment and capacity of government staff to monitor and evaluate - how do we grow that capacity? Social science evaluation tool start up at Glasgow Uni - how do we outsource and finance that and show benefits?	Learning from COVID experience about collecting data on vulnerable populations - eg. local teenagers speaking with elderly - to identify who needed food and medical attention	
	Coastal zone management NI identified gaps and what we have currently - may show that certain sections of coastline you have a lot of data - relevance to decision making as that stock take can inform research.	Practitioner feedback needs to be able to be used within academic spaces more	
	Business case - justifying why spending £ - comes down to non-monetary benefit analysis - difficult to put cost on it - recreational and social welfare value	Mitigation and adaptation challenges - easier to monitor mitigation, adaptation much more complex - difficult to measure success if a flood didn't occur,	
	Historic England - internal M & E but challenging getting short term answers to long term problems - if it doesn't flood you can't show that as a success	Ensuring research helps to inform policy evidence gaps - targeted research	
	Using science and evidence base currently but also future scanning	Funding and resource for long term continual monitoring and evaluation	
	Long term projects - not dependent on academic or political cycles	Horizon scanning - what has worked well elsewhere?	
	Breaking down siloes - sharing evidence		

	What do we do next with M & E data?		
	Priorities		